

ENhancing our understanding of Trade Impacts
on Climate, industries, and the Environment

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D1.1- STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

WP1–Framing – theoretical underpinnings, public perceptions, and policy needs

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Responsible Author	Katerina Zovoili	Email	kzovoili@epu.ntua.gr	
	ICCS	Phone	-	
Contributors	Alexandros Nikas, Konstantinos Koasidis, Georgios Trachanas (ICCS)			
Reviewer(s)	Dimitra Spatharidou (HOL); Lukas Hermwille (WI); Panagiotis Fragkos (E3M); Aleksander Sniegocki (REFORM)			
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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable will serve as a reference document for all consortium partners to familiarise with the process of stakeholder engagement throughout the ENTICE project. External actors may also use the document to understand this stakeholder engagement process—before, throughout, or after their (potential) engagement—as well as to get a solid understanding of why stakeholder inclusion in climate-economy modelling is important and how it can be achieved.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

Delivering societally relevant and policy-actionable outcomes is a core objective of the ENTICE project. This document presents a stakeholder engagement strategy that is designed to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between consortium partners and external actors in support of that objective. The primary scope of the stakeholder processes in ENTICE is to ensure the relevance of the project’s research and overall activities for policymaking, promote mutual understanding and trust between modellers and societal actors (including policymakers), and incorporate direct stakeholder input to ensure that the scientific process reflects real-world social and political dynamics.

The stakeholder engagement plan builds on a “transdisciplinary listening mechanism”, which is intended to offer a structured approach to collaboration between project partners and external stakeholders. In ENTICE, stakeholders will be selected on an ad-hoc basis from a well-maintained, ethics-compliant database managed by ICCS and designated persons across the consortium. This database will draw on the established networks of all consortium partners. Engagement itself will remain flexible in nature and timing, meaning that several methods will support our stakeholder process—including bilateral interviews, workshops/focus group discussions, surveys/questionnaires, and/or public events.

Together with project coordinators (E3M), ICCS will lead the implementation of the stakeholder engagement strategy, in close collaboration with all project partners. This process begins with the selection of appropriate stakeholders to populate the stakeholder database, collaborative development of a policy-relevant research agenda broken down into a series of themes that may serve different purposes and project objectives, and ad-hoc selection of stakeholders to invite in a series of online seminars corresponding to said themes.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

In today's interconnected global economy, understanding the trade-climate nexus is more critical than ever. Trade policies significantly influence environmental outcomes, while climate change affects trade flows. However, the complex relationship between these areas remains insufficiently explored, often due to data limitations, gaps in economic modelling, and the evolving nature of global supply chains. The ENTICE project aims to bridge these knowledge gaps by advancing our understanding of the trade-climate-industry (TCI) nexus. It examines how trade policies impact environmental sustainability and how climate policies shape global trade dynamics. By developing fact-based insights and innovative modelling tools, ENTICE supports informed decision-making at this crucial intersection of trade, climate, and sustainability.

E3M – E3-MODELLING AE	EL	
CMCC – FONDAZIONE CENTRO EURO-MEDITERRANEO SUI CAMBIAMENTI CLIMATICI	IT	
WI – WUPPERTAL INSTITUT FUR KLIMA, UMWELT, ENERGIE GGMBH	DE	
REFORM – FUNDACJA INSTYTUT REFORM	PL	
VUA – STICHTING VU	NL	
HOL – HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
ENEXTGEN – ENEXTGEN S.R.L.	IT	
UoS – UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON	UK	
UNIVR – UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI VERONA	IT	
SEURECO – SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
ICCS – EREVNITIKO PANEPISTIMIAKO INSTITOUTO SYSTIMATON EPIKOINONION KAI YPOLOGISTON	EL	
POLIMI – POLITECNICO DI MILANO	IT	
Purdue – TRUSTEES OF PURDUE UNIVERSITY	US	
ZEW – LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUR EUROPAISCHE WIRTSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG GMBH MANNHEIMRL	DE	
UU – UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT	NL	
ORDESCYS – ORDESCYS SARL	CH	

Executive Summary

Trade has been a cornerstone for global economic growth and welfare improvement, as it increases the accessibility to a wide range of resources, promotes economies of scale, enhances efficiency in production and consumption of goods, facilitates the access of consumers to a variety of goods, accelerates knowledge spillovers and technology diffusion, and enhances competition and product specialisation. Despite not being equally distributed across countries and industries, these benefits are fuelling a continuous acceleration of trade in the global economy over the last six decades (according to WTO, data volume of trade has more than quintupled since the 1990s). At the same time the growth of international trade has increased considerably the interconnectedness and interdependencies among firms and countries worldwide. Industries and consumers depend on materials and intermediate goods whose production/supply is scattered around the globe creating complex global value chains. In parallel, and especially following the Paris Agreement, climate policies have been developing rapidly in developed and developing countries affecting the operation and decision-making processes of all economic agents. As the global economy is becoming increasingly interconnected, with the expansion of complex global value chains, climate policies gradually become an important factor affecting trade flows. Trade policies also have large climate and environmental impacts as well as implications for climate mitigation efforts. Therefore, the interactions between trade (policies) and climate (policies) have been a prime concern for decision-makers that influence policy design and formulation, industries, scientists, and civil society.

A principal component of ENTICE is to map the policy landscape and associated needs onto instrumental capabilities (i.e., modelling frameworks, expanded datasets) and scenarios. The project thus aims to ensure policy relevance by systematically involving stakeholders throughout the research process—from the initial scoping of research questions, through data and modelling development, scenario development, onto the discussion and dissemination of results. A well-defined stakeholder engagement plan is therefore essential to support this goal, enabling meaningful knowledge exchange and collaboration between modellers and key stakeholder groups, including—but not limited to—policymakers, industry representatives, and civil society organisations.

The project will establish and operate a transdisciplinary listening mechanism, in which it will engage with a diverse group of stakeholders at the EU (e.g., policymakers DG TRADE, CLIMA, GROW, and ENER; or European industry associations; NGOs; etc.) and national level (e.g., from Ministries of Environment, Trade, Energy, Economy/Finance, etc. in Member States), to capture the most pertinent questions to address, in the trade-climate-environment-industry-sustainability nexus.

A structured approach can offer a consistent format for engagement between project partners and stakeholders. The latter will be selected from a database managed by ICCS, in charge of operationalising the stakeholder engagement strategy, in collaboration with the project coordinator and all partners. Stakeholder engagement will be guided by a detailed Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, documented in this report, as well as powered by a dynamic, GDPR-compliant stakeholder database, tailored to the needs of the project, populated by contacts of project partners, and documented in Milestone Report (MS4).

Throughout the project, stakeholder engagement will take place with a view to ensuring policy and societal relevance and promoting transparency and ownership of data, models, and results. It will be done by means of bilateral (semi-structured interviews, physical meetings, questionnaires); and multilateral (e-meetings, webinars, surveys, physical workshops) communication channels.

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1 Introduction

Despite the wide recognition of the complex interactions between trade (policy) and climate (policy), the state-of-the-art capabilities in terms of available data as well as of macroeconomic models face substantial limitations, such as lack of granular information (especially for industrial sectors and supply chains), dependence on conventional trade theories, limited empirical evidence on trade-climate interactions, limited representation of the value and material chain in key (existing and emerging) sectors, heavy reliance on modelling frameworks not accounting for endogenous technical change, limited understanding of the role of developing countries in trade, etc. Partly owing to these gaps but also due to limited prior focus on and attention to climate-trade interplays, science in support of climate and/or trade policymaking has also featured considerable constraints, notably in terms of scenario exercises that touch upon issues of relevance to these interplays. Despite identified and well-established gaps in both instrumental technical and research capacity and scenario space, and given the growing urgency of analysing and understanding how trade (policy) interacts with climate change (policy), non-scientific actors (and/or academics outside the boundaries of this consortium) can shed more light on other, less discussed research questions—and, in turn/as a result, concrete research capacity needs.

In this respect, ENTICE intends to map the policy landscape and associated societal/policy needs onto instrumental capabilities (i.e., modelling frameworks, datasets) and scenario elements, towards ensuring relevance to policy, research, and society, and by systematically involving stakeholders throughout its process—from scoping research questions, to developing new data and modelling capabilities, designing scenarios, and to discussing and disseminating its results. Here, we document a stakeholder engagement strategy that can support this goal, by enabling meaningful knowledge exchange and collaboration between modellers and key stakeholder groups, including—but not limited to—policymakers, industry representatives, and civil society organisations.

This strategy will facilitate our efforts not only to deliver research that directly responds to stakeholder needs and feeds into the trade and climate policy discourse, but also to serve transparency, legitimacy, and open science, on which it places considerable emphasis.

This deliverable aims to provide both project partners and external stakeholders with a clear overview of the stakeholder engagement strategy of the ENTICE project. At the heart of this strategy is the “**transdisciplinary listening mechanism**”—a structured process designed to foster constructive dialogue and knowledge exchange between external stakeholders and project partners/modellers. Its primary goal is to ensure that the research conducted within ENTICE generates insights that are directly relevant to policy design. The stakeholder engagement strategy in ENTICE is guided by two core objectives:

- Enhancing **policy relevance** of research by systematically integrating stakeholder perspectives
- Promoting **knowledge exchange** across science, policy, business, and civil society

This document outlines the guiding principles for stakeholder engagement strategy. After this section, we define the purpose and principles of stakeholder engagement in ENTICE (Section 2), before outlining the strategy in detail (Section 3), including a definition of stakeholders and stakeholder groups, a presentation of the stakeholder database (purpose, objectives, setup, coordination, population, maintenance, structure, and compliance with GDPR), and an overview of the engagement techniques and indicative timeline of the thematic online seminars.

2 Stakeholder engagement: purpose and principles

Modelling science that is disconnected from, or insufficiently engages with, society can undermine research efforts by disassociating them from real-world policy contexts. In many cases, stakeholders have only been marginally involved—typically through basic consultations—thereby limiting the depth of their contribution (Galende-Sanchez & Sorman, 2021). Consequently, the models produced often fail to reflect the complexities of actual decision-making environments (Doukas et al., 2018). The ENTICE project seeks to strengthen our understanding of how trade and trade policies affect climate (policies) and the environment—either positively or negatively—by developing innovative data and modelling tools and exploring policy-relevant and scientifically stimulating questions co-designed with relevant stakeholders. This involves combining traditional macroeconomic models with contemporary trade theories, empirical analysis, high-resolution data, and stakeholder knowledge, concerns, motives, and interests to generate insights that can effectively support policymaking. ENTICE aims to integrate specific approaches and practices for stakeholder engagement to enhance the policy relevance and shared ownership of its data, modelling tools, and research outcomes. This section outlines the role of stakeholder involvement within the project and defines the core principles guiding the “transdisciplinary listening mechanism.”

2.1 Purpose

The global governance landscape is highly dynamic, with numerous existing and emerging institutions and initiatives relevant for the Trade-Competitiveness-Industry (TCI) Nexus (Otto and Oberthür 2022). Geopolitical tensions about trade have resurfaced, especially with the recent adoption of landmark laws—e.g., the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) in the USA or the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) in the EU—or the recent shift in the discussion around trade, fostering a more dynamic environment but also potentially higher expectations from stakeholders regarding the pace/scope of trade policy assessments. In this landscape, the project’s stakeholder engagement process and in particular its transdisciplinary listening mechanism aims to listen to (as in “monitor”) key developments of international governance in the TCI Nexus and facilitate dialogue among the consortium’s (modelling) teams and external stakeholders at different levels, as to how these developments may affect the project’s scenario design process and underlying assumptions. Drawing on experiences and lessons learnt from recent and ongoing research projects that are strongly oriented towards stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and knowledge co-production (such as PARIS REINFORCE, IAM COMPACT, or DECIPHER), this mechanism establishes a transdisciplinary process that will enable to pinpoint politically pertinent research questions and modelling scenarios and to adjust the corresponding research activities throughout the project duration to accommodate real-world developments.

2.2 Principles

The principles outlined in this section guide both the selection of stakeholders and the formation of stakeholder groups. These principles serve as the foundational values for interactions between project partners and stakeholders. A commonly used framework in science-policy engagement—Credibility, Relevance, and Legitimacy (CRELE)—offers a useful lens for evaluating the effectiveness of stakeholder involvement (Sarkki et al., 2013). Given that these criteria can sometimes conflict with one another, it is important to strike a careful balance among them.

- *Credibility* refers to the reliability of the stakeholder engagement process. This depends on identifying the right participants, ensuring a balanced mix of perspectives, adequate expertise, and continuity of involvement throughout the project. ENTICE, like similar initiatives, aims to include a diversity of views to maintain high standards of credibility.
- *Relevance* relates to how useful the project outcomes are for the intended audiences. While policymakers—especially within the EU—are the primary users, outputs should also be of value to other groups, including industry actors and civil society.
- *Legitimacy* involves ensuring fairness and inclusivity in the stakeholder engagement process. A transparent, well-structured strategy helps prevent and resolve conflicts and reinforces stakeholder trust. One key to achieving legitimacy is to involve a diverse and balanced group of participants, allowing all voices to be heard.

3 Overview of the strategy

3.1 What's a stakeholder?

Before outlining the stakeholder engagement strategy, it is essential to clarify the definition of a stakeholder within the context of ENTICE. For the purposes of this project, stakeholders will be considered as external actors who influence and/or are affected by trade and climate (policies). This includes policymakers involved in decision-making processes of relevance to trade (policy) and climate (policies), representatives from industries impacted by these policies (and their interactions), academics/researchers involved in understanding these interactions and providing the scientific evidence underpinning important decisions and policies, as well as civil society organisations that bring in the perspectives of the wider public. While technically all individuals and organisations connected to ENTICE—including members of the project consortium—could be regarded as stakeholders, this strategy refers to “stakeholders” as those outside the consortium. Those directly involved in the design and implementation of the project are instead referred to as “project partners.”

3.2 Stakeholder groups

ENTICE aims to facilitate the cross-fertilisation of the insights produced during the project. It will **highlight the interlinkages between different disciplines** (natural & environmental sciences, engineering sciences, and social sciences including economics, behavioural science, trade theory, political science, etc.) and the added value of applying and substantially enhancing those with cutting-edge methodologies and comprehensive integrated approaches to address the climate and environmental impacts of trade policies (and vice versa). Furthermore, it will **nurture a shared understanding** of the challenges and opportunities associated with the development of sustainable, efficient, and equitable trade policies amongst actors with a stake in climate and environment issues, including:

- Policymakers at the EU (various DGs of the European Commission) and national level (such as in Ministries of Finance, Trade, Climate, Environment, and Energy), directly involved in decision-making processes, who need to become familiar with the different economic methods and understand how to best use them to advance their policy agenda.
- Researchers and particularly trade/macro-economists and modelling scientists actively involved in analysing (the interactions of) trade-economy-climate-environment, who need to broaden their perspective, enhance their methods and tools, expand the scope of their research, contribute to stretching the frontiers of science, and overcome knowledge gaps and shortcomings.
- Businesses and industries affected by climate change, climate policies, trade, and trade policies directly, who are expected to be up to-date with policy priorities, anticipate developments, position themselves accordingly, and reap benefits while ensuring efficiency.
- Civil society and the wider public, who become more informed, get closer to science underpinning policies with society-wide implications, and thus grow more empowered to shape (and more eager to accept) these policies (i.e., knowledge and policy co-production, delegation of power, public acceptance).

In essence, the project will thus involve four groups of stakeholders as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Types of Stakeholder Groups expected to be heavily involved in ENTICE.

3.3 Stakeholder database

As part of this stakeholder engagement strategy, a stakeholder database representing the broad diversity of interests, attitudes, genders, and work capacities has been established (as part of project milestone MS4), to subsequently be enriched/updated throughout the project.

3.3.1 Purpose

The stakeholder database fulfils multiple strategic purposes that collectively contribute to the project's success, enabling the identification and categorisation of relevant stakeholders across sectors, regions, industries, and expertise levels, and creating a comprehensive map of the project's ecosystem. This mapping facilitates targeted communication and engagement activities throughout the project lifecycle, ensuring that (a) invitations to be meaningfully involved, (b) key messages, and (c) actionable policy insights reach the most appropriate audiences. Hence, the purpose of said database is to constitute a focal point that collects and provides all necessary information that will enable the project to place actors from all relevant stakeholder groups (scientists, experts, policymakers, researchers, industries, citizens, organisations) at the heart of our activities. Below, we outline concrete information on the structure of the ENTICE stakeholder database and the process to set it up to ensure transparency and GDPR-compliance.

3.3.2 Objectives

- **Ensuring comprehensive stakeholder representation:** Development and maintenance of a dynamic database that reflects the diversity of stakeholders across interests, sectors, regions, gender, expertise, and capacities, ensuring inclusivity in engagement.
- **Enabling strategic stakeholder mapping:** Identification, classification, and mapping of stakeholders based on their roles, influence, expertise, and relevance to the project, thereby supporting effective targeting of communication and participation.
- **Facilitating targeted and effective communication:** Provision of a structured system for directing project communications—including invitations to events, surveys, and feedback requests—to the most appropriate stakeholders.
- **Supporting continuous engagement and co-creation:** Serving as the backbone for the project's Transdisciplinary Listening Mechanism and ensuring stakeholder inputs are integrated across relevant tasks and activities and throughout the project lifecycle.
- **Promoting synergies and collaboration:** Underpinning efforts for synergies in science, by identifying stakeholders involved in similar initiatives or projects, enabling collaboration, alignment, and knowledge exchange.
- **Ensuring compliance and transparency:** Collection, storage, and management of stakeholder data in a manner that is fully transparent and compliant with GDPR, while enabling project partners to use the data ethically and effectively.

3.3.3 Initial setup and coordination

The stakeholder database development process is coordinated by ICCS, acting as a designated project partner that oversees the collection, integration, and management of stakeholder information from all project partners. The process begins with the following steps:

- **Appointment of Responsible Persons:** Each partner designates one primary contact person that is responsible for accessing and maintaining the Stakeholders Repository List. Partners may also appoint a backup contact if desired, ensuring continuity in the database management even in the absence of the primary contact. This approach distributes responsibility while maintaining centralised oversight, thus creating an efficient management structure.
- **Access rights management:** ICCS grants editing/access rights to the Responsible Persons from each partner organisation. A confirmation email and password for editing access is provided to each responsible person.
- **Template Distribution:** A standardised Excel template is shared with all partners, and the information (to be accessed by Responsible Persons only) is password-protected and stored in the project's internal data management system, ensuring consistent data collection and formatting.

3.3.4 Stakeholder identification

Partners identify stakeholders with whom they have an existing working relationship or ongoing communication, as they will be responsible for contacting their contacts that are deemed of relevance to

and/or potentially interested in the project's activities. Hence, random or publicly sourced contacts should not be included in the stakeholder database, in line with GDPR considerations.

The reason for this process is that the compilation of this list of individuals from previous contacts essentially constitutes a stakeholder map. As such, this list is not to be used for general communication (i.e., newsletters etc.), but rather serves to identify potentially interested parties, who may be *personally* contacted at a later stage of the project on an *ad-hoc* basis.

Alternatively, for project partners with broader networks and contacts, a templated letter was drafted to facilitate initial contact with interested stakeholders, requesting permission to add them to the project lists for future dissemination of material/activities (e.g., newsletter). Should they respond positively, including them in the stakeholder database will also be considered.

3.3.5 Maintenance and updates

The stakeholder database is a dynamic resource that evolves throughout the project lifecycle. Its maintenance involves regular updates and data retention management.

Throughout the project, the database will be continuously enriched with new stakeholders identified during project implementation (while, if necessary, removing others opting out). As the project progresses and expands its reach, new stakeholders will emerge that can contribute to or benefit from the project's activities and outputs. These new stakeholders will be systematically added to the database, expanding the project's network and potential impact.

Data retention and removal processes are essential aspects of database maintenance, particularly in the context of GDPR compliance. Should a stakeholder indicate to the partner contacting them that the project is not of their interest or they no longer wish to be contacted about the project, the corresponding entry will be promptly deleted from the database, and the opt-out confirmation will be kept for record-keeping purposes. Similarly, if a stakeholder becomes unreachable, their entry will be removed from the database.

3.3.6 Core attributes

After a first set of high-level interactions with selected experts from the stakeholder pool of the project (from the database) focusing on baseline scenario considerations, a series of thematic online seminars (6-8 in total) will be organised throughout the project lifecycle, each designed to address specific political developments of strategic interest to the ENTICE stakeholders. We will approach this audience by inviting relevant and influential policymakers to join the Listening mechanism of the project (Task 1.3), to guide and/or evaluate our research process. Two main attributes contribute to a successful stakeholder engagement throughout the project.

First, the database is populated with the aim to ensure diversity and, to the extent possible, representativeness. We are notably targeting policymakers, both at the EU level and at the national level (in Member States and Associated Countries) as well as policy and industry stakeholders from outside Europe, considering that the implications of trade and trade policies must also be comprehended along value chains from a global perspective and with a special focus on developing economies. An equally crucial consideration is securing a gender-balanced representation among stakeholders.

Second, the sophisticated relational structure of the stakeholder database methodical approach to data organisation will facilitate deeper insights into stakeholder perspectives and enable more targeted

engagement strategies as the project progresses.

3.3.7 Structure

The ENTICE stakeholder database incorporates the following data fields, carefully selected to enable comprehensive stakeholder management.

Table 1. Database structure

Variables	Categories	Notes
Name		
Surname		
Gender	Man Woman Non-binary/non-conforming Other Not sure/Prefer not to respond	
Organisation		
Position within an organisation		
Main Field of activity/interest	Agriculture Citizen Association Climate Construction Economy Energy Engineering Food Health International Trade Labour Model development Policy government	
Secondary Field of activity		Open-ended cell to partners' discretion (optionally)
Country		
City		
Stakeholder Category	Academia Cities Network Consultant EU policymaker International Agency Local Energy Agency Local Government National Agency National Government NGO Private sector/Industry Regional Government Research Centre Trade Union	
Email		
Partner Reference		Partner responsible for contacting the stakeholder
Date of addition		Version of record (addition date)

3.3.8 GDPR compliance

The ENTICE project, alongside its stakeholder database, is fully compliant with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

The project adheres to fundamental data collection principles that align with GDPR requirements laid out by regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. All stakeholder data will be collected, primarily through existing professional/personal relationships. This approach ensures that data collection is legitimate and transparent, respecting stakeholder rights.

A different process will be implemented to accommodate a stricter interpretation of data protection regulations for various partners. Instead of directly sharing personal contact details with the central stakeholder database, some Responsible Persons were alternatively authorised to:

1. Send initial outreach messages directly to their relevant contacts.
2. Invite these contacts to voluntarily engage with ENTICE through the invitation letter.
3. Provide the consortium with only a list of organisations they contacted, rather than individual contact information.

This alternative approach respects national and/or organisational data protection requirements while still enabling effective stakeholder engagement.

To facilitate this alternative approach, an outreach letter template was also provided (see Annex), to outline the voluntary nature of participation and confirm that contact details are only used for ENTICE-related purposes in full compliance with data protection regulations.

3.4 Engagement techniques

Selecting the most appropriate engagement technique for each stakeholder or stakeholder group is essential, given the varying roles, interests, and capacities of different actors—such as policymakers, industry representatives, or civil society organisations. To ensure meaningful and effective engagement, three key criteria should guide the choice of method:

- The stakeholder group's level of interest in participating in the project
- The degree of influence the group may have on project outcomes
- The most suitable engagement and knowledge-gathering approaches for that group

Although **the project's stakeholder engagement will primarily take place via thematic online seminars, in the form of virtual stakeholder workshops**, engagement strategies may be tailored to maximise impact and relevance by aligning the chosen techniques with the criteria listed above. An overview of the engagement techniques planned for use in ENTICE is provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Stakeholder engagement techniques in ENTICE

Engagement technique	Most appropriate application of technique
Information board and contact points	Establish contact points with each project partner
Correspondence by phone and/or email	Distribute project information to government officials, organisations, agencies, and companies Invite stakeholders to meetings and other project activities
Bilateral or multilateral interviews	Solicit views and opinions by enabling stakeholders to speak freely and confidentially about controversial and sensitive issues Build personal relations with stakeholders
Formal meetings	Present project information to a group of stakeholders Allow the group of stakeholders to provide their views and opinions and input to the modelling process and scenario design Build impersonal relations with high-level stakeholders Distribute technical documents
Public events	Participate in relevant high-impact events, publish policy briefs and scientific papers, establish synergies Present project information to a large audience of stakeholders Allow a group of stakeholders to provide their views and opinions Build relationships with industries/associations (including at the local level) Distribute non-technical project information
Thematic Online Seminars	Present project information to a group of stakeholders Allow foundational stakeholder groups to provide their views and opinions of targeted baseline information on a specific thematic/regional issue Use participatory exercises to facilitate group discussions, brainstorm issues, analyse information, and develop recommendations and strategies monitoring political developments <i>This is the default stakeholder engagement technique in ENTICE.</i>

A series of thematic online seminars (6-8 in total) will be held, aiming to cover specific political developments of interest, by monitoring ongoing political developments (in particular related to trade and climate) and suggesting themes to the Work Package Leaders of the ENTICE project for approval (see Table 3). For instance, these seminars could cover and explore the relevance of modern policy issues such as:

1. Revisions to, extra-regional impacts of, and international responses to CBAM revisions
2. Clean Trade and Investment Partnerships
3. Upcoming Industrial Decarbonisation Accelerator Act
4. Escalating trade tensions between the USA, the EU, and China
5. The EU Net Zero Industrial Act and its international impacts
6. Ongoing negotiations on Trade Agreements (e.g., Mercosur)
7. Trade-related effects of green industrial and competitiveness policies (e.g., IRA)
8. UNFCCC COPs, new NDCs/targets, updated Long-Term climate targets, climate finance goals, climate impacts/adaptation, and trade implications
9. Developments in international trade rules and the relevance of the WTO
10. Climate clubs

11. Geopolitical shifts
12. Tariff wars

Table 3. Indicative list (scope, timing, participants) of thematic online seminars

Scope	Timing (TBC)	Participants
1. Defining baseline/reference scenarios	Sep 2025	Project partners, academia (other researchers outside the project) <i>Potential participants: policymakers and industry actors</i>
2. Presenting & discussing the TCI framework	Oct 2025	Primary participants: Project partners, academia (other researchers outside the project) <i>Potential participants: policymakers</i>
3-6. Identifying research questions & designing overarching scenario elements for modelling exercises	2026-2027	Project partners, academia (other researchers outside the project), policymakers, industry actors, civil society
7-8. Disseminating results & discussing insights and policy recommendations	2028	Project partners, academia (other researchers outside the project), policymakers, industry actors, civil society

ANNEX: GDPR-Compliant Stakeholder Engagement Letter for Partners with Stricter Data Protection Requirements

Subject: Invitation to join the ENTICE stakeholder list – Climate & Trade Policy Dialogue

Dear (Name),

We are contacting you as part of the EU-funded project **ENTICE**, which focuses on modelling trade policy and its interaction with climate and energy policy. We are building a targeted network of experts and stakeholders who may wish to be informed or involved in activities such as policy dialogues, webinars, or workshops.

Participation is entirely voluntary. Your contact details will only be used for ENTICE-related purposes in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

If you are interested in actively participating in our process or simply finding out more about this project, please visit our website, at <https://www.enticeproject.eu/>, and subscribe to our newsletter.

You may also follow us on the following social media:

[LinkedIn](#)

[Bluesky](#)

[Instagram](#)

Best regards,

Name

Organisation

On behalf of the ENTICE Project

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